

PREVALENCE OF ECTOPARASITES AND ENDOPARASITES AMONG LOCAL DOGS IN OKITIPUPA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Dogs are arguably the most common pet animals worldwide. They may harbour a wide range of parasites with zoonotic potential, thus causing health risks to humans. In some parts of Nigeria, dog meat is a well sort after delicacy. This study evaluated the species, abundance, distribution and the degree of ectoparasites and endoparasites infestation among local commercial dogs in Okitipupa Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria, from January 2022 to April 2022.

Ectoparasites were manually collected from different parts of the body of the dogs; while endoparasites were observed by faecal, intestine and blood examinations. Among the 31 dogs examined, three parasites were identified in the faecal samples: *Giardia lamblia* (54.83 %), *Ancylostoma caninum* (48.38 %) and *Taenia* spp. (45.16 %) respectively. In the intestine, *G. lamblia*, *A. caninum* and *Taenia* spp. have a varied prevalence of 51.61 %, 41.93% and 29.03 % respectively, while two haemoparasites: *Babesia* spp. (51.61 %) and *Anaplasma* spp. (15.16 %) were identified in the examined blood samples. Three species of ticks were the only ectoparasites observed in this study. *Ixodes scapularis* was the most prevalent (38.70 %) while *Dermacentor variabilis* and *Rhipicephalus sanguineus* were equally prevalent (16.12%). The result of this study

shows that most of the examined dogs harbour a relatively high level of endo and ectoparasites. There is thus the need for effective and efficient public education and measures to mitigate against zoonotic transmission and possible outbreak of infestation among domestic keepers of dogs and consumers of dog meat.

Keywords: Local dogs, Ectoparasites and endoparasites, Public health, Okitipupa, Zoonosis

INTRODUCTION

Dog or domestic dog (*Canis familiaris* or *Canis lupus familiaris*) is a domesticated descendant of the wolf which is characterized by an upturning tail. Over 15,000 years ago, dogs were the first species of animal to be domesticated (Thalmann and Perri, 2018). They are the most common pet animals in the world and serves other functions such as assisting the police and the military, therapeutical usage and aiding disabled people, earning them the title of "man's best friend" (Freedman and Wayne, 2017). Dog meat is a well sought- after delicacy, particularly in Nigeria where dogs are eaten for various reasons such as its medicinal values, as traditional rites or as a source of protein. As reported by Ehimiyein *et al.*, 2014; Pereira *et al.*, 2016; and Bagbe *et al.*, 2022), dogs are are belied to harbour a wide range of parasites with zoonotic potential that could lead to diseases such as cutaneous and visceral larva migrans, hydatid disease and tungiasis, thus causing health risks to humans.

Based on its habitat, parasites can be classified as endoparasitic; living inside the host or ectoparasitic; living on or outside the host. Both endoparasites and ectoparasites have adverse effects on dogs' health and can transmit pathogens to humans.

Rhipicephalus sanguineus, *Sensu lato*, *Ctenocephalides* sp., *Trichodectes canis*, *Linognathus setosus* and *Heterodoxus spiniger* have been reported as the most common ectoparasites of domestic dogs in many tropical countries (Heukelbach *et al.*, 2012; Bagbe *et al.*, 2022) while

among the most commonly reported endoparasites of dogs across the world, are gastrointestinal nematodes such as *Ancylostoma caninum*, *Toxocara canis*, *Trichuris vulpis*, and protozoans such as *Babesia* sp., and *Giardia* sp. (Duncan *et al.*, 2020; Ayokunle, *et al.*, 2022).

The zoonotic potential of ectoparasites and endoparasites affecting dogs has been extensively investigated in different geographic locations due to close contact between dogs and humans. This highlights the importance of monitoring parasite distribution and evaluating parasitic infections of domestic dogs as opined by Dantas-Torres and Otranto, 2014; Bagbe and Bagbe, 2019). This study therefore evaluated the **prevalence of ectoparasites and endoparasites among local dogs in okitipupa local government area of ondo state, Nigeria** from January 2022 to April 2022.

METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted in three selected areas (Igodan-lisa, Okunmo and Ayeka) within Okitipupa Local Government Area of Ondo state, Southwest Nigeria between January 2022 to April 2022. Okitipupa (6°33'N and 4°43'E) has a savannah vegetation feature and the climate is typical with intense rainfalls from April to October and daily temperatures between 23 °C and 37 °C. Land area is about 803 km², and total human population is over 316,100 ranking 4th in the state.

Study population

A total of 31 local dogs made up the study population; thirteen (13) from Igodan-lisa, eight (8) from Okunmo and ten (10) from Ayeka with no bias toward sex, age, type, use and location of the dogs.

Collection of Ectoparasites

The ticks were collected directly off the dog body using appropriately sized forceps. Unattached ticks were removed by combing and brushing the fur of the dogs over a white enamel tray or sheet of paper. Ticks were separately preserved in 70% alcohol before identification.

Isolation and Identification of Ectoparasites

Collected ectoparasites were transferred from the 70% alcohol into watch glasses containing 10% potassium hydroxide (KOH) solution for 24-36 hours at room temperature until the morphological features were clear. Ticks were identified based on an entomologist morphological feature using keys and atlases as described by Soulsby (1982).

Collection of Endoparasites

Endoparasites were observed by faecal, intestinal and blood examinations. Spatula was used to collect faecal samples directly from the rectum of dogs into labelled sterile bottles. Blood samples were collected from the dog's cephalic vein into sample bottles containing ethylene diamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA). Small portions of the dog's intestine were collected immediately after killing. All samples were transported in icebox to the Biological Sciences Laboratory, Department of Biological Sciences, Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa and processed for physical and microscopic examination.

Laboratory analysis of faecal sample

Collected faecal samples from dogs were examined using a modified sucrose floatation method. Approximately 2-3 g of faeces from each subject was mixed in 5 ml of water. The mixture was sieved through a tea strainer into 15 ml centrifuge tube and centrifuged at 2,500 rpm for 10 minutes. The supernatant was discarded and sucrose solution (specific gravity 1.27), was added to the tube to the mark of 14 ml. The sediment was mixed with the sucrose solution and centrifuged at 2,500 rpm for 5 minutes, and more sucrose solution was added until convex meniscus was visible at the top of the tubes. Coverslips were gently placed on top of the tubes and then allowed to stand for 30 seconds. The coverslips were removed and transferred to separate microscope slides for examination. Egg and oocyst counts were identified based on microscopic and morphological

appearances. The species and the number of each species encountered were manually counted and recorded for each sample.

Analysis of blood sample

Blood samples were analyzed using Giemsa thin smear method as described by Cheesbrough, (2006). A drop of blood was placed on a grease-free clean glass slide and touched with the edge of another slide. It was held at an angle of 30° and pushed gently to the left, till the blood was exhausted. The film was allowed to dry, and the slide was fixed with methanol for 5 minutes before staining with dilute 10% Giemsa stain. The slides were examined under oil immersion (x100) objective. Haemoparasites were identified using morphological features as described by Liapis, (2019).

Data analysis

The data obtained from laboratory analysis were analyzed using simple descriptive statistics of frequency and percentage. Prevalence was calculated for all data as the number of infected individuals divided by the total number of dogs examined and was expressed in percentage by multiplying by 100. Results were presented in tables.

RESULTS

Of the 31 dogs examined in all locations, three parasites were identified in the faecal samples: *Giardia lamblia* had the highest prevalence of 54.83 % followed by *Ancylostoma caninum* with 48.38 % and *Taenia* sp. with the least prevalence of 45.16 % (Table 1).

In the intestines, *Taenia* sp. was the least occurring intestinal parasite with 29.03 %, *Giardia lamblia* had a prevalence of 51.61 % making it the highest occurring intestinal parasite, while *Ancylostoma caninum* was found in 13 of the dogs resulting in 41.93 %.

Two blood parasites were identified in the blood samples collected from the dogs' specimen, *Babesia* sp. was the highest occurring parasites of the two species found with a prevalence of 51.61 %, while *Anaplasma* sp. was found in 14 of the dogs making 15.16 %.

For Ecto-parasites; three species of ticks were was found on the bodies of various dogs ranging from *Ixodes scapularis* with 38.70 %, the highest of all three, *Dermacentor variabilis* 16.12 % and *Rhipicophalus sanguineus* which has the same prevalence as *Dermacentor variabilis* (Table 1).

Table 1: Prevalence of endo- and ecto-parasites among dogs in Okitipupa Local Government (n=31)

Parasites	Infected dogs	Prevalence (%)
Faecal		
<i>Ancylostoma caninum</i>	15	48.38
<i>Giardia lamblia</i>	17	54.83
<i>Taenia</i> sp.	14	45.16
Intestinal		
<i>Ancylostoma caninum</i>	13	41.93
<i>Giardia lamblia</i>	16	51.61
<i>Taenia</i> sp.	9	29.03
Haemoparasites		
<i>Anaplasma</i> sp.	14	45.16
<i>Babesia</i> sp.	16	51.61
Ectoparasites		
<i>Ixodes scapularis</i>	12	38.70
<i>Dermacentor variabilis</i>	5	16.12
<i>Rhipicophalus sanguineus</i>	5	16.12

96.77 % of the domestic dogs examined in this study were infected with one or more ecto-and endo-parasites. In each of the study site, the infestation rate was 100% except in Ayeka where one of the dogs examined was not infected as indicated in (Table 2).

Table 2: Distribution of the Prevalence of endo- and ecto-parasites among dogs in Okitipupa LGA, Nigeria based on location (n = 31)

Location	Number examined	Number Infected	Prevalence (%)
Igodan-lisa	13	13	100
Okunmo	8	8	100
Ayeka	10	9	90
	Total = 31	Total = 30	

A total of 31 dogs were sampled, 13 from Igodan-lisa, 8 from Okunmo and 10 from Ayeka. All locations showed presence of the same endo and ectoparasites in dogs, which means transmission of these parasite is high and most of the dogs serve as suitable hosts for the identified parasites. Igodan-lisa shows significant difference from other locations with *Giardia lamblia* being the highest prevalent among all the parasites identified in Igodan-lisa (10/13), in Ayeka the blood parasite *Anaplasma* sp. had the highest distribution in that location (7/10) and in Okunmo *Giardia lamblia* was highly distributed in the faecal and intestinal samples observed (5/8) respectively. The high prevalence of these parasites is a potential threat to both the animal population and human population because most of the parasites are zoonotic.

DISCUSSION

Several reports on the prevalence of parasitism in dogs from different parts of Nigeria have been recorded. The presence of gastrointestinal parasites *Ancylostoma caninum*, *Giardia lamblia* and *Taenia* sp. in Okitipupa area of southwest Nigeria agrees with previous reports from some other parts of the country (Kamani *et al.*, 2011; Bagbe *et al.*, 2022). *Ancylostoma caninum* in this study has a high prevalence of 41.93 % which is higher than Ugbomoiko *et al.* (2008) who reported 16.9 % prevalence in Nigeria but in agreement with Mustaph *et al.* (2011) who reported 54.8%

prevalence in Maiduguri. *Ancylostoma caninum* in dogs can cause anaemia, diarrhoea, and slow growth. However, the high prevalence of *Giardia lambia* (51.61 %) in dogs recorded in this study is an important find, this is because *Giardia lambia* is normally contacted from water bodies in Nigeria.

Taenia spp. had a prevalence of (29.03 %); this disagrees with the reports of Mustapha *et al.* (2016) who had 7.3 % in Maiduguri and Ehimiyein *et al.* (2018) who reported a prevalence of 19.67 % in Zaria. Differences in frequency of gastrointestinal helminth infection within a country is possible due to the differences in weather condition required for the biology of the parasites, veterinary facilities and public awareness to take care of dogs (Ugbomoiko *et al.*, 2008).

Anaplasma sp. and *Babesia* sp. were the haemoparasites recorded in the study with 45.16 % and 51.61 % prevalence respectively; the high prevalence of *Anaplasma* sp. in this study is a new finding. *Babesia* sp. prevalence is in consonant with the 42.1 % previously reported by Kamani *et al.* (2011) in North Central Nigeria, but this disagrees with Edosomwan and Chinweba (2012) who recorded prevalence of 28.0 % in Benin City Southern Nigeria and 8.9 % prevalence reported by Jegede *et al.* (2014). The reason for these variations could be due to the season of the year in which the research was carried out, management system and clinical status of the researched dogs (Ogunkoya *et al.*, 2006; Bagbe *et al.*, 2022).

Earlier reports showed that Nigerian dogs are commonly infested with *Xenopsylla cheopis*, *Pulex irritans*, *Tunga penetrans*, *R. sanguineus*, and species of *Amblyomma*, *Ixodes*, *Otodectes*, *Demodex*, and *Sarcoptes scabiei* var. *canis* (Ugbomoiko *et al.*, 2008; Bagbe *et al.*, 2022). In the present study, 38.70 % of the sampled dogs were positive for *Ixodes scapularis* and *R. sanguineus* and *Dermacentor variabilis* each having 16.12 % prevalence. The prevalence of *R. sanguineus* agrees with 16 % reported by Ogbu *et.al* (2020) in Plateau. *Rhipicephalus* ticks have been described to parasitize humans and may transmit rickettsia diseases.

Several canine parasites have zoonotic importance and therefore portend public health hazards. Some of these parasites also affects the general health and productivity of the dogs. This reflects the need for the implementation of appropriate intervention measures through health education, sensitization of owners and provision of affordable veterinary clinics by the government to reduce the risk of zoonotic transmission. Dogs should be regularly dewormed and acaricide solution can be sprayed or rubbed on pets to reduce worms and tick-borne diseases. Fumigation of dog kennels and houses would help to reduce the occurrence. Dogs' food, especially meat and fish should be properly cooked before serving. Dog handlers should also handle dogs with care to avoid contracting any infection from the dogs.

CONCLUSION

This study revealed that majority of the dogs in the study area haboured ecto- and endo-parasites of public health importance. The ecto- and endo-parasites detected in this study were *Ancylostoma caninum*, *Giardia lamblia*, *Taenia* sp., *Anaplasma* sp., *Babesia* sp., *Ixodes scapularis*, *Dermacentor variabilis*, and *Rhipicophalus sanguineus*. The high prevalence of gastrointestinal parasites obtained in this study could be due to environmental contamination providing ready access to infective stages of the parasites, since most of these dogs reportedly roam and defecate indiscriminately within these areas which could result in cycles of infection and re-infection. Also, examined fresh faeces collected from the rectum provided a higher chance of recovering more infective parasitic stages than faeces exposed to the environment in which some parasite may have been destroyed.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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